

Periodontal Muscle Training can Strengthen the Periodontal Support, Fit your Teeth

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Abstract

According to statistical analysis, a total of 505 patients in general practice were asked to respond to a list of 25 obligatory nourishment for a child while going to have the first teeth, for its effectiveness in dealing with patient's periodontal health especially include chewing hard food. They were also asked to select the three effective nutrition for periodontal tissue. This indicates of patient perceived importance of the periodontal health were derived and each compared with actual effectiveness as determined from a sample of 250 patients opinion.

Although the majority of patient's 18 of 25 nutrition as being very effective, there was no significant association with patient perceived nourishment effectiveness and actual effectiveness. The implications for patient training are discussed.

Extra Questions	Total Adults
I try to eat healthy these days and pay attention to nutrition	84.00%
In general I feel I eat right	60.00%
I try to eat healthy breakfast daily	57.00%
I follow a regular exercise routine	62.00%
I pay attention how many times i chew food	30.00%
I visit my dentist two times a year	36.00%
I regularly eat organic food	32.00%
I prefer to eat at home rather restaurant	65.00%

Introduction

By comparing the effect of long term workout in the fitness gyms and the habit of consuming hard rational food daily with a weekly schedule, could be very likely and would be support the oral health indeed. What to do to have aesthetically and functionally prevention method for further gum and periodontal diseases, which could be less aggressive and conservative, cheap and home treating methods. In case one cares about his body's physique, also he can care about the Gum structure as well.

Case Report

To have a review, Bundles attached to teeth and their dis attachments provoke further injuries. Let's take a look at these bundles, if we peel away alveolar septa and papillae & marginal part, we can see the bundles (periodontal ligament) which is composed of bundles of connective tissues fiber that anchor the teeth within the jaw [1]. Each bundle is attached to cementum covering the root of the tooth. The other end is embedded in bony tooth sockets (alveolar socket). These bundles of fibers allow the tooth to withstand the forces of biting and chewing.

Endomysium, the connective tissue sheaths that surround each skeletal muscle fiber separating the muscle cells from one another. It also contains capillary nerves and lymphatic's.

As an illustration, organization of skeletal tissues, intact skeletal muscle. Biceps brachii is attached to bones through tendons, Connective tissue. The entire muscle is surrounded by connective tissue called epimysium [2]. The muscle is organized into bundles called premium. Each fascicles contains many individual fibers surrounded by connective tissue called Endomysium.

In some muscles there might only be relatively few fibers such as in muscle of the eye in which these are only 10 of fibers.

In some of the bigger muscles in the body there may be thousands of fibers, for instance, there can be up to 400000 fibers in the bicep muscle in front of the arm.

Each of these fibers is surrounded by sheaths of fibrous tissue membrane or fascia called Endomysium (endo- means within).

Article Information

DOI: 10.31021/ijcmc.20181107
Article Type: Case Report
Journal Type: Open Access
Volume: 1 **Issue:** 2
Manuscript ID: IJCMC-1-107
Publisher: Boffin Access Limited

Received Date: January 23, 2018
Accepted Date: June 01, 2018
Published Date: June 13, 2018

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Citation: Sabzchamanara N. Periodontal Muscle Training can Strengthen the Periodontal Support, Fit your Teeth. Int J Clin Med Cases. 2018 Jun;1(2):107

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Therefore, by having regular training in fitness centers our extremities muscles can strength and can have an aesthetic and supportive function for skeletal system.

Childs Obligatory Nourishment	Total Adults Intake
Cheese	71%
Yogurt	85%
Leafy Greens	45%
Apples	52%
Almonds	45%
Carrot	33%
Celery	14%

Results

As within skeletal growth, the muscles in the body also grow at irregular rates. The enlargement of muscles (hypertrophy) makes them thicker but muscle fibers can also get longer. With certain types of training and genetics, muscle mass can change [3].

According to the aging of muscular system, one reason is reducing the strength and power of the muscles; therefore, by training the endomysiums within the periodontal ligament with special training as well as eating hard foods and chewing them we can train them exactly like fitness club.

The experiment above 18-25% of those patients who had

answered to the test satisfactory had a healthier gum structure in comparing with the unsatisfactory ones. By making some clinics besides gyms and sport centers which prescribe daily, weekly, monthly schedules to fit the gum muscles with special measurement individually for each patient can make a revolution in gum and oral health history.

Conclusion

Due to the proper nourishment for the newborn babies we acknowledge that they are effective to form the jaws, gums, teeth, and help them nourish well and form the proper shape. Therefore, repeating this process could be an aid for preventing any lack of support or lease to make further diseases as this nutrition only strength the body mass around teeth.

Acknowledgement

The author appreciates the CAMLOG for choosing the article for the first time.

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